

Spectrophotometric Determination of Zinc Dimethyl Dithiocarbamate (Ziram) with Hydroxyamidine and 4-(2-Pyridylazo)naphthol

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There are several methods for the determination of carbamates in the literature^{1,2}. In the present communication, we report a comparatively simple, rapid, selective and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the determination of ziram. The method is based on the fact that the metallic dithiocarbamates liberate their respective metal ions in the solution when prepared in dilute acidic medium³. The procedure involves the complexation reaction of ziram with *N*-hydroxy-*N*, *N'*-diphenylbezamidine (HDPBA) in chloroform at pH 9.5 ± 0.2 maintained by carbonate-bicarbonate buffer. The chloroform extractable species is then reacted with 4-(2-pyridylazo)naphthol (PAN) to give intense red colour, whose absorbance is measured at 550 nm.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of ziram and zinc(II)-HDPBA/PAN complexes studied separately showed $\lambda_{\max}$ around 550 nm against reagent blanks. A $(2.8-5.6) \times 10^{-3}$ M HDPBA in chloroform was found to be sufficient for the complete extraction of ziram complex at pH range of 8.5-10.5. The organic extract was then reacted with PAN. At least $(0.8-1.5) \times 10^{-3}$ M PAN in ethanol was required for complete and maximum colour development at pH 9.0 ± 0.5. Larger amount of PAN resulted in increased blank absorbance. Various organic solvents, viz. ethyl acetate, 1-pentanol, 4-methylpentan-2-one, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, benzene, toluene and xylene were tried for the extraction of the complex. Of these, chloroform was chosen due to more selective separation and higher distribution of the complex in it. A shaking period of 2 min was sufficient for complete extraction of the complex and the complex was stable for at least 6 h at room temperature (28°).

The method followed Beer's law up to 3.0 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ ziram with a correlation coefficient value of 0.97. The molar absorptivity of this method is $9.1 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with Sandell's sensitivity of 0.003 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. A minimum of 0.02 μg ziram can be estimated by the present method. The relative standard deviation for ten replicate measurements is 1.4%.

The following ions do not interfere in the determination of 1.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ ziram (amounts in mg are given in parenthesis): Ni^{II}, Co^{II} (0.5); Cu^{II}, Hg^{II}, Bi^{III} (0.8); Sb^{III}, Mn^{II}, Cr^{VI} (1.0); Se^{IV}, phosphate, oxalate (1.2); tartarate, citrate, thiourea (3.0); thiosulphate, iodide (5.0). However, Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} interfered which were masked with 1 ml each of 5% (w/v) sodium thiosulphate and iodide respectively.

The interference due to some common dithiocarbamate pesticides, namely dibam (sodium dimethyl dithiocarbamate), thiram (disodium *N*-methyl dithiocarbamate), vapam (sodium *N*-methyl dithiocarbamate), ferbam (ferric dimethyl dithiocarbamate), maneb (manganese ethylenebis dithiocarbamate), zineb (zinc ethylenebis dithiocarbamate) in the determination of 1.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ ziram were tested; only the serious interference from zineb was observed. A minimum of 2.0 mg of pesticides without containing metal ions could be tolerated. Other metallic dithiocarbamates did not interfere up to 1.0 mg since ziram was selectively extracted at pH 9.5 ± 0.2 into chloroform with HDPBA, prior to its determination with PAN.

Application : The proposed method was applied for the determination of ziram from fortified crop and soil samples and highly satisfactory results were obtained and the results compared with a reported method² (Table 1).

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss-Jena spekol with EK-5 attachment and matched 10-mm quartz cuvettes and a digital Systronics 335 meter were used.

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The standard solution of ziram was prepared in dilute HNO₃ and dilute HCl acids. The contents of zinc was examined by decomposing it with concentrated HNO₃ acid and titrating with EDTA using eriochrome black T as indicator. The working standard solution of known strength was prepared by appropriate dilution. *N*-Hydroxy-*N*, *N'*-diphenylbezamidine (HDPBA) was synthesised⁴ and its 0.007 M solution in chloroform was employed for extractions. A 0.1% (w/v) solution of 4-(2-pyridylazo)naphthol (PAN) in 95% (v/v) ethanol was used for colour development. A mixture of 0.2 M sodium carbonate and 0.2 M sodium bicarbonate was used as buffer for pH adjustment.

Procedure : A known volume of sample solution (containing up to 30 μg of ziram) was taken. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 9.5 ± 0.2 in a 10 ml final volume using carbonate-bicarbonate buffer (1-3 ml). The solution was shaken vigorously for 2 min with chloroform solution (5 ml) of HDPBA. The chloroform layer was separated, a 0.1% PAN solution (3 ml) added to it and shaken for a few seconds. The reddish extract was made up to 10 ml with ethanol and its absorbance measured at 550 nm against the reagent blank.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF ZIRAM (ZINC DIMETHYL DITHIOCARBAMATE) FROM FORTIFIED CROP AND SOIL SAMPLES

Samples	Amount of ziram (μ g)			Recovery by present method %	Average recovery %
	Added	Found by present method*	Found by reported method		
Crop samples					
Apple	5	4.8 (1.5)	4.7	96.0	96.7
	10	9.7 (1.5)	9.6	97.0	
	15	14.6 (1.6)	14.2	97.3	
	20	19.3 (1.5)	18.8	96.5	
	25	24.2 (1.6)	24.0	96.8	
Wheat	5	4.9 (1.5)	4.8	98.0	98.1
	10	9.8 (1.6)	9.4	98.0	
	15	14.7 (1.7)	14.6	98.0	
	20	19.5 (1.6)	19.2	97.5	
	25	24.8 (1.4)	24.3	99.2	
Soil samples :					
S ₁	10	9.7 (1.7)	9.5	97.0	97.1
	20	19.6 (1.6)	19.2	98.0	
	30	28.9 (1.6)	28.5	96.3	
S ₂	10	9.6 (1.6)	9.5	96.0	96.6
	20	19.7 (1.7)	19.4	98.5	
	30	29.2 (1.7)	28.6	95.3	

*Number of determinations = 6; figure in parenthesis shows % RSD value.

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